

DIABETES MELLITUS: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON TYPES, COMPLICATIONS, TREATMENT AND DIAGNOSIS

*¹Gothi Dhruvi R., ²Chauhan Sneha A., ³Prajapati Ayush R., ⁴Chavda Dhara D.,
⁵Panchal Utsav S., ⁶Mrs. Ami Patel

*^{1,2,3,4,5,6}B. Pharm Student, Department of Pharmacy, Shri Sarvajanic Pharmacy College,
Gujarat, India.

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*Corresponding Author

Gothi Dhruvi R.

B. Pharm Student, Department of
Pharmacy, Shri Sarvajanic Pharmacy
College, Gujarat, India.

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by elevated blood glucose levels resulting from defects in insulin secretion or action. The prevalence of diabetes is rapidly increasing worldwide, especially in developing countries like India. This study aims to compare the risk factors associated with diabetes mellitus among rural and urban populations. A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted among adults aged 18–65 years to assess the influence of demographic, lifestyle, and metabolic variables. Parameters such as BMI, physical activity, diet, family history, hypertension, and socioeconomic status were evaluated. Results indicate that urban populations show higher prevalence due to sedentary lifestyles, obesity, and unhealthy dietary patterns, while rural areas are increasingly affected due to changing food habits and reduced physical activity. The study highlights the need for tailored preventive strategies targeting both communities. Promoting awareness, lifestyle modification, and early

screening can significantly reduce the growing burden of diabetes in India.

KEYWORDS:

1. DM – Diabetes Mellitus
2. IDDM – Insulin Dependent Diabetes Mellitus
3. NIDDM – Non Insulin Dependent Diabetes Mellitus

4. HG - Hyperglycemia
5. IR– Insulin Resistance

INTRODUCTION

As per the WHO, diabetes mellitus (DM) is defined as a heterogeneous metabolic disorder characterised by common feature of chronic hyperglycaemia with disturbance of carbohydrate, fat and protein metabolism.

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is commonest endocrine disorder that affects more than 100 million people worldwide (6% population). It is caused by deficiency or ineffective production of insulin by pancreas which results in increase or decrease in concentrations of glucose in the blood. It is found to damage many of body systems particularly blood vessels, eyes, kidney, heart and nerves. Diabetes mellitus has been classified into two types i.e. insulin dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM, Type I) and non-insulin dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM, Type II).

Type I diabetes is an autoimmune disease. Type II diabetes is characterized by peripheral insulin resistance and impaired insulin secretion.

The presence of DM shows increased risk of many complications such as cardiovascular diseases, peripheral vascular diseases, stroke, neuropathy, renal failure, retinopathy, blindness. Insulin replacement therapy is the mainstay for patients with type 1 DM while diet and lifestyle. Modifications are considered the cornerstone for the treatment and management of type 2 DM. Various types of hypo glycaemic agents such as biguanides and sulfonylureas are also available for treatment of diabetes.

EPIDEMIOLOGY

- DM is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality world over. It is estimated that approximately 1% of population suffers from DM. The incidence is rising in the developed countries of the world at the rate of about 10% per year, especially of type 2 DM, due to rising incidence of obesity and reduced activity levels.
- It is anticipated that the number of diabetics will exceed 250 million by the year 2010.
- It is estimated that 366 million people had DM in 2011; by 2030 this would have risen to 552 million.
- The number of people with type 2 DM is increasing in every country with 80% of people

with DM living in low- and middle-income countries. DM caused 4.6 million deaths in 2018.

- It is predicted that the prevalence of DM in adults of which type 2 DM is becoming prominent will increase in the next two decades and much of the increase will occur in developing countries where major of patients are aged between 45 to 64 years.

Fig. 1: Epidemiology of diabetes: A global View.

It constitutes about 10% cases of DM. It was previously termed as juvenile-onset diabetes (JOD) due to its occurrence in younger age, and was called insulin dependent DM (IDDM) because it was known that these patients have absolute requirement for insulin replacement as treatment.

Type 1 diabetes is an organ-specific autoimmune condition. It happens when your body attacks your pancreas with antibodies. The organ is damaged and doesn't make insulin. It affects 2 million people, including about 304,000 children and teens in the U.S.

Type 1 diabetes cannot be prevented. Type 1 diabetes symptoms happen quickly, in a few days to weeks. They include:

- Feeling thirst and hunger often
- Peeing more
- Blurry vision
- Fatigue
- Unexplained weight loss

About 30% of people with type 1 diabetes have a life-threatening condition that causes loss of consciousness, called diabetic coma, as their first symptom.

Type 2 DM

Diabetes is a chronic disease. It is characterized by high levels of sugar in the blood. Type 2 diabetes is also called type 2 diabetes mellitus and adult-onset diabetes. That's because it used to start almost always in middle and late adulthood. However, more and more children and teens are developing this condition. Type 2 diabetes is much more common than type 1 diabetes, and is really a different disease.

During digestion, food is broken down into basic components. Carbohydrates are broken down into simple sugars, primarily glucose. Glucose is a critically important source of energy for the body's cells. To provide energy to the cells, glucose needs to leave the blood and get inside the cells. Type 2 diabetes occurs when your body's cells resist the normal effect of insulin, which is to drive glucose in the blood into the inside of the cells. This condition is called insulin resistance.

The symptoms of diabetes are related to high blood glucose levels. They include:

- Excessive urination
- Thirst hunger and weight loss
- Increased susceptibility to infections
- Yeast or fungal infections

Pathophysiology

- Main features: Insulin resistance, reduced insulin production, β -cell failure.
- Effect: \downarrow Glucose uptake by liver, muscle, fat \rightarrow hyperglycemia.
- Fat metabolism: \uparrow Fat breakdown \rightarrow worsens hyperglycemia.

➤ Type 1 vs Type 2

Type 1: Autoimmune β -cell destruction, insulin deficiency.

Type 2: Insulin resistance + impaired secretion, usually in obese adults.

- Neuro link: Insulin resistance \rightarrow $A\beta$ plaque formation & tau hyperphosphorylation \rightarrow cognitive decline.
- Pathogenesis of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Main metabolic defects:
 1. Impaired insulin secretion (delayed response to glucose).
 2. Insulin resistance (peripheral tissues fail to respond).

Complications of Diabetes

Due to chronic hyper glycaemia, all body tissues undergo biochemical and structural changes, leading to two main types of complications:

1. Acute Metabolic Complications

- Diabetic Ketoacidosis (DKA): Seen in Type 1 DM due to severe insulin deficiency and excess glucagon.
- Causes fat breakdown → ketone body formation metabolic acidosis.
- Symptoms: Nausea, vomiting, deep breathing, confusion, coma.
- Hypoglycaemia: Due to excess insulin, missed meals, or stress.

2. Chronic (Late) Systemic Complications

- Develop after years of uncontrolled diabetes; cause major morbidity and mortality.
- Atherosclerosis: Early, severe arterial damage → coronary disease, stroke
- Microangiopathy: Thickening of small vessel basement membranes (skin, kidney, nerves).

DIAGNOSIS

According to the American Diabetes Association (ADA), the fasting glucose concentration should be used in routine screening for diabetes; but postprandial blood sugar, random blood sugar and glucose tolerance test are also used for blood sugar determination. For the diagnosis of diabetes, at least one criterion must apply:

1. Symptoms of diabetes (polyuria, polydipsia, unexplained weight loss, etc) as well as casual plasma glucose concentration = 11.1 mmol/L (200 mg/dL).
2. Fasting plasma glucose = Its normal range is 70-110 mg/dl with no caloric intake for at least 8 h.

The World Health Organization (WHO) classification includes both clinical stages (normoglycaemia, impaired glucose tolerance/impaired fasting glucose (IGT/IFG), diabetes) and etiological types of diabetes mellitus, identical to the ADA except that WHO group includes classification formerly known as gestational impaired glucose tolerance (GIGT) and GDM: fasting glucose = 7.0 mmol/L (126 mg/dL) and/or 2-h glucose = 7.8 mmol/L (140 mg/dL) after a 75-g.

Treatment

Lifestyle Modifications

- Diet: Eat whole grains, fruits, and vegetables; avoid refined sugars and fats.
- Exercise: At least 150 minutes of moderate activity weekly improves insulin sensitivity
- Weight Loss: Losing 5–10% body weight reduces insulin resistance.

Pharmacological Treatment

- Metformin: First-line drug; lowers hepatic glucose and improves insulin sensitivity.
Sulfonylureas (e.g., Glimpiride): Stimulate insulin secretion.

The comparative study highlights that diabetes mellitus is influenced by different but overlapping risk factors in rural and urban populations. Urban populations show a higher prevalence of diabetes, largely due to lifestyle-related factors such as sedentary behavior, unhealthy dietary patterns, obesity, stress, and reduced physical activity. Increased consumption of processed foods, higher rates of overweight and central obesity, and limited time for exercise contribute significantly to the urban burden of diabetes.

In contrast, rural populations, while traditionally considered at lower risk, are experiencing a gradual rise in diabetes prevalence. This increase is associated with changing lifestyles, reduced physical labor due to mechanization, poor awareness about diabetes, limited access to healthcare facilities, and delayed diagnosis. Dietary transitions toward refined carbohydrates and fats, along with lack of routine health screening, further elevate risk in rural areas.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that diabetes mellitus is no longer confined to urban settings and has become a growing public health concern in rural communities as well. Therefore, preventive strategies must be population-specific. Urban interventions should focus on lifestyle modification, stress management, and obesity control, while rural strategies should emphasize health education, early screening, improved healthcare access, and awareness about modifiable risk factors.

Overall, addressing diabetes effectively requires integrated, region-specific public health policies that target both behavioral and socioeconomic determinants of health in rural and urban populations.

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Full name	Enrollment no
GOTHI DHRUVI RAMESHBHAI	222450290018
CHAUHAN SNEHA ARVINDKUMAR	222450290013
PRAJAPATI AYUSH RAKESHBHAI	212450290024
CHAVDA DHARA DILIPSINH	222450290014
PANCHAL UTSAV SHANAKRBHAI	212450290016

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